

The Coalition of Non-State Actors and Climate Case Law in
France:
The Promising Legal Shift in the Climate Debate

**The African Institute Series on
Climate Change
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Case Overview

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v.

**Case filed
October 26, 2015
Against French
Government for Implicit
Decision of Rejection**

**Judicial Review of
Implicit Decisions of
French Authorities**

**Failing to take all
Appropriate Measures
To Design Air Pollution
Policies Aiming to Reduce
Concentrations of Fine
Particles And Nitrogen
Dioxide**

Non-State Actors' Claims

Annulment for Excess of Power

Implicit Rejection Decisions

May it Please the Court

Your Honor!

Order the Design/Revision of all the Plans of Protection of Atmosphere

In 12 Urban Areas
Paris, Marseille, Lyon, etc

NO WAY!

Enjoin to Take Necessary Measures/Strick down Fine Particles & Nitrogen Dioxide Concentrations

**Have You Ever Consider—
We've Done Enough with
Ecological Transition?**

Non-State Actors' Claims

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If You've Done Enough, to Prove it, Just Design/Revise Impugned Climate Plans in 12 Areas!

We Comply to European Law and Domestic Law.

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European Law! How about EU Directive of May 21, 2008, on Cleaner Air? Or the Environment Code?

You Don't Even Have A Standing in the Matter!

Is It Enough to Transpose European Law to Say We Are Doing a Lot?

We've done Quite A Bit.

Just Take Necessary Measures & Reduce Concentrations.

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Conseil d'Etat Ruling
July 12, 2017

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**I Find France in
Breach of European
and Domestic Law**

**France Should
Transmit to
European
Commission before
31 March 2018**

**I Rule Out the
Penalty Payment
Request**

**Friends of the Earth
Is Found to Have
Standing to File
Proceedings**

**I Quash All Implicit
Rejection Decisions
By French
Government**

**Government Should
Take Necessary
Measures to
Design/Revise Air
Quality Plans**

**A Year and 3 Months
Later: French
Government Had
Provided the EU
Commission with
Evidence That
Nothing Had Been
Actually Done**

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THANK YOU SO MUCH!

**What Do We Do
Now?**